

Incidental Detection of Bilateral Complex Congenital Cataract in an Asymptomatic Pediatric Patient

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Article Info :

Received : 23/09/2025

Revised : 16/10/2025

Accepted: 16/10/2025

Available online: 29/10/2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17478923

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Clinical Image

Bilateral congenital cataract is a rare condition that can exhibit diverse morphologies and may remain asymptomatic when mild, underscoring the importance of early detection. An 8-year-old child, with no significant medical or family history, was referred following a routine school health examination. The patient reported no visual complaints. Ophthalmologic evaluation revealed a best-corrected visual acuity of 10/10 in both eyes, with normal pupillary light reflexes and intraocular pressure.

Slit-lamp examination showed a quiet anterior segment, but detailed lens assessment revealed bilateral congenital cataracts combining sutural, cerulean, and lamellar components (Figures 1–2). Fundus examination was normal in both eyes.

Although congenital cataracts may sometimes cause visual impairment, certain type, such as sutural or cerulean cataracts, can remain asymptomatic while preserving excellent visual acuity. This incidental finding highlights the value of routine ocular screening in children, as early identification enables close monitoring and timely intervention should progression occur.

This case illustrates the benign course of some complex congenital cataracts and reinforces the importance of school-based eye examinations in detecting silent ophthalmic abnormalities.

Figure 1–2: Slit-lamp photographs of both eyes showing complex congenital cataract morphology, combining sutural, cerulean, and lamellar components

Ethical Consideration: This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards of the responsible committee on human experimentation (institutional and national) and the Helsinki Declaration of 1975, as revised in 2000. The authors declare that they have obtained the necessary authorizations for publication.

Conflict of Interest: There is no conflict of interest

Funding Support: There is no funding support for this study